

Performance of Crop Insurance Scheme in Thoothukudi District of Tamil Nadu

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Abstract

Farmers are the backbone of the country. In order to protect their livelihood and reduce farmer's suicide, it is necessary to engage a farmer in insurance scheme. Scheme is a thing that should be managed well by proper management and continuous evaluation. On assessing the performance levels, the implementation and reach of the scheme could be easily identified. The study has been conducted at Vilathikulam and Srivaikundam blocks Thoothukudi district as randomly selected with loanee sampling farmers' size 30.

This study shows that maximum number of farmers [53.3%] earns an annual income of Rs. 25000 - 50000/-. Cent per cent of the farmers were adopted in crop insurance scheme. Farmers have received their insurance claims and still half or quarter of the amount is in progress of transfer. Majority of the farmers feel that the insurance amount received have compensated only 40 % of their crop loss.

There may be a need for more awareness among various farmers, efficient regulation mechanism, timely repayment of compensation and crop losses made by wild animals like wild pig should also be included in the losses and there may be a need for Separate Insurance Department in order to overview the progress of the scheme.

Keywords: performance, crop losses, crop insurance, loanee farmers, defaulters.

Introduction

Crop insurance scheme to deal with risks associated with weather fluctuation is imperative for alleviating the distress caused to the farmers. Also, at present, only 23% of cropped area in India has access to insurance. According to sources, Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana will increase the insurance coverage to 50 per cent of the total crop area of 194.40 million hectare from the existing level of about 25-27 per cent crop area.

Farmers are the backbone of the country. In order to protect their livelihood and reduce farmer's suicide, it is necessary to engage a farmer in insurance scheme. In such view, the study “Performance of Crop Insurance Scheme in Thoothukudi District of Tamil Nadu” was carried out with the objective of to study the performance of crop insurance scheme in Thoothukudi district; and

Methodology

Random sampling technique has been followed in analyzing the performance of crop insurance scheme in Thoothukudi district. Thoothukudi, district was selected purposively as it occupies a pride place in area and production of the state and farmers of this district are aware of crop insurance schemes. And also to facilitate convenience of our project work since it is located very near to our college. This study has been conducted at Vilathikulam and Srivaikundam blocks Thoothukudi district as randomly selected with loanee sampling farmers’ size 30.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 Land Holding Pattern

Based on the area [in acres] of land the farmers hold, farmers have been classified as follows

S. No	Category	Number	Percentage
1	Marginal [<2.5 acres]	3	10.00
2	Small [2.5 to 5 acres]	8	26.70
3	Medium [5 to 8 acres]	12	40.00
4	Large [> 8 acres]	7	23.30
Total		30	100.00

Inferred from table 1, it is inferred that most of the farmers are medium farmers i.e. they hold 5 to 8 acres and followed by small farmers [2.5 to 5 acres]. Medium farmers could face fewer difficulties in paying premium amount than the marginal farmers. And so these areas could be made more adoptable to stick to the policies of crop insurance scheme.

Table 2 Crops Cultivated

The crops being cultivated in different blocks are as follows

Name of the Block	Type of Land	Sources of Irrigation	Crops Cultivated
Srivaikundam	Wetland and gardenland	Canal, Well	Rice, Blackgram, Banana, Cocoa,
Vilathikulam	Rainfed	Rain	Chilli, Blackgram, Greengram, Cumbu, Maize, Sorghum

Table 2 shows that Srivaikundam block use some sources of irrigation other than rain to cultivate crops. But in Vilathikulam block, the only source of water is rain. Therefore there are many chances of natural calamities like drought or flood. And so the farmers in these areas must be well educated about crop insurance scheme in order to compensate their yield loss. Adoption in this area will be more if there is proper awareness with logical reasons.

Table 3 Annual Income

S. No	Annual Income (in Rs.)	Number	Percentage
1	<25,000	5	16.70
2	25,000 - 50000	16	53.30
3	>50000	9	30.00
Total		30	100.00

Table 3 shows that maximum number of farmers earn an annual income of Rs. 25000 -50000/- and followed by farmers earn an annual income >50000. This shows that they face few difficulties in paying monthly premium since their annual income is not sufficient. Though they face few difficulties in paying premium, the crop insurance scheme will help them during their yield loss period. And so, if the farmers are well educated about the benefits of this scheme, there will be a great increase in the adoption rate.

Table 4 Sources of Information

Category	Frequency	Number	Percentage
Listening to Television	Often	30	100.00
Listening to Radio	Often	30	100.00
Participation in agricultural meetings, exhibitions, seminars	Often / occasionally	30	100.00

Table 4 shows that the farmers often listen to television, radio for agriculture related news. They also participate in the agriculture related meetings conducted by agriculture departments. Therefore television, radio and agricultural meetings are the good means of communication through which ideas of crop insurance scheme can be disseminated well.

Table 5 Awareness and Adoption

S. No	Category	Number	Percentage
1	Awareness of the scheme	30	100.00
2	Adoption of the scheme	30	100.00

From Table 5, it is inferred that cent per cent of the sample farmers' were awareness and adoption of crop insurance scheme.

Table 6 Enrollment

S. No	Particulars	Answers
1	Enrollment in previous year	30 farmers
2	Enrollment in present year	30 farmers
3	Insured crops	Rice, Banana, Cocoa, Chilli, Blackgram, Greengram, Cumbu, Maize, Sorghum
4	Premium amount	Different for different crops Kharif - 2 % Rabi - 1.5 % Horticultural crops - 5 %
5	Disasters faced	Drought [2016 - 2017]
6	Losses experienced	Pest and disease attack, yield loss

From Table 6, it is inferred that all 30 farmers have been insured last year as well as this year. The crops which have been cultivated in their field as mentioned above in table 5 have been insured. The premium amount differs for different crops as mentioned in the table. The major disaster faced by them was Drought [2016 - 2017].

Table 7 Insurance Amount

S. No	Particulars	Answers
1	Farmers who received insurance amount	30
2	Total insurance amount credit	Differs for different crops Still half of the amount is in pending.

Table 7 shows that all the farmers have received their insurance claims and still half or quarter of the amount is in progress of transfer.

Table 8 Compensation

S. No	Category	Number	Percentage
1	<25 %	10	33.30
2	25 - 50 %	12	40.00
3	>50 %	8	26.70
	Total	30	100.00

From Table 8, it is inferred that majority of the farmers feel that the insurance amount received have compensated only 40.00 per cent of their crop loss. And so it is understood that the farmers are expecting some additional amount in order to look after their livelihood during disaster periods.

Table 9 Details about Loan

S. No	Category	Number	Percentage
1	Loanee farmers	6	20.00
2	Non - loanee farmers	24	80.00
	Total	30	100.00

From table 9, it is inferred that most of the farmers who have insured their crop have not obtained crop loan. This means that there is not necessary that loanee farmers alone must insure their crop.

Reasons quoted by the farmers for adoption of Crop Insurance Scheme

To compensate yield loss, to supplement family income and to provide source for next agricultural input.

Conclusions

This study shows that maximum number of farmers [53.3%] earns an annual income of Rs. 25000 - 50000/-. Cent per cent of the farmers were adopted in crop insurance scheme. Farmers have received their insurance claims and still half or quarter of the amount is in progress of transfer. Majority of the farmers feel that the insurance amount received have compensated only 40% of their crop loss. Constrains faced by the farmers were they feel difficulty in receiving the adangal from the concerned officer and in institution were the sanctioned amount from the Government is delayed, they have fixed number of target farmers, there is lack of understanding about the scheme among the farmers and there is lack of involvement among the farmers.

There may be a need for more awareness among various farmers, efficient regulation mechanism, timely repayment of compensation and there may be a need for Separate Insurance Department in order to overview the progress of the scheme.

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